

Effect of sodium chloride on morphophysiological indicators of wheat and maize genotypes

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The aim of the work was to study the effect of sodium chloride on the physiological and biochemical characteristics of wheat and maize genotypes, to identify varieties that are resistant to salinity. To create new salt-tolerant varieties of wheat and maize, a comparative analysis of the physiological and biochemical parameters of the parental and hybrid plants was carried out. Physiological parameters such as chlorophyll content and relative water content have been studied in parental forms and hybrids. When studying salt-tolerance of hybrids and parental forms, differences were detected in the relative amounts of chlorophyll (a+b), carotenoids and RWC. The effect of salt on the amount of chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b, and carotenoids, which are the main physiological indicators, is manifested in different ways in both hybrids and parental forms. Based on the physiological indices determined during the grain filling stage, the highest tolerance was manifested by the parental forms, Garabagh, Gobustan, and the hybrids, ♀Garabagh×♂Gobustan, ♀Garabagh×♂Mirbashir, ♀Garabagh×♂Sharg. A slight increase in the content of soluble sugars was detected in all genotypes of maize under the action of salt. The highest sugar content was observed in the hybrid Zagatala 68 x Gurur.

Keywords: *Wheat, maize, salinity, hybrid, genotype, chlorophyll, carotenoid, tolerance*

INTRODUCTION

Salinity is one of the abiotic stress factors decreasing plant productivity. The salinization of soils over time is particularly dangerous. The limitation of agricultural and fertile lands is an obstacle to meeting the food requirements of the population (Khan et al., 2010). In particular, the rapid growth of the population and the need in ensuring food security make more urgent the development of salt-tolerant varieties capable to grow in saline soils, and their extensive use. According to rough estimates, 521,700 hectares of plains in the Azerbaijan Republic were in a saline state (Azizov, 2002). In 2007, this parameter increased to 661.9 thousand hectares and accounted for 46.6 % of the land (Mammadov, 2007).

One of the most effective measures taken to achieve high productivity under stress is the development of plants capable to adapt to salinity. The expression of genes regulating stress tolerance increases under high salt concentrations and ensures salt tolerance of plants (Garrat et al., 2002).

According to some authors, developing more plastic wheat varieties, suitable for the regions of the republic is required because of the disturbance

of ecological balance and the presence of abiotic stress factors. Therefore, stress tolerance in plant breeding is of great importance (Rustamov et al., 2017). Currently, in our country, extensive research has been carried out on salt-tolerance of local wheat varieties as well as brought from abroad Huseynova et al., 2008). Thus, numerous studies conducted in the world and in our country showed the perspectives of the development of wheat varieties adapted to salinity.

The purpose of the research was to study the effect of sodium chloride on the physiological and biochemical characteristics of wheat and maize genotypes and to identify varieties tolerant to salinity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The objects of the study were parental and hybrid wheat forms grown under normal and salinity (0,98 % NaCl) conditions. The objects of the study were the genotypes of wheat Gobustan, Mirbashir-128, Barakatli-95, Garabagh, Gyrgyzgul, Sharg and their generation hybrids Garabagh×Gobustan, Gobustan×Barakatli-95,

Gobustan×Gyrmyzygul, Barakatli-95×Gobustan,
Gobustan×Garabagh, Garabagh×Mirbashir,
Garabagh×Sharg.

The second generation (F₂) hybrids obtained from seven combinations during the study were planted on a field of 1 m², under normal conditions, on October 25, 2019. For the experiments, 300 g NaCl was added to the soil before sowing during tillering, earing, and grain-filling stages. Sowing was conducted following the scheme P♀-F2-P♂ 5×25 cm. Watering was performed at the tillering, earing, and grain-filling stages. Agrotechnical care was conducted in the experimental field. Samples were taken at the grain-filling stage of the vegetation. Measurements were done *in vivo* and *in vitro* for the comparative study of the changes in physiological parameters caused by the salt effect.

The object of the research was also the genotypes of maize Zagatala-420, Zagatala-514, Zagatala-68, Gurur, and first-generation F₁ hybrid Zagatal-68×Gurur. Plant seeds germinated under laboratory conditions in Petri dishes and pots with soil using 150 mmol sodium chloride solution. Germination energy was determined by counting three-day-old seedlings, and seed germination ability by counting seven-day-old seedlings as a percentage. The content of soluble sugars was determined in two-week-old seedlings.

0.1 g of leaf samples of hybrid and parental forms taken from plants grown under both normal and saline conditions were homogenized using a pestle and mortar in 96 % alcohol by adding CaCO₃, centrifuged at 200 g, and a pure extract of chlorophyll pigments was obtained. The optical density of a solution of chlorophyll in alcohol was measured on an SP-2000 spectrophotometer at 665, 649, 440 nm, and the amounts of chlorophyll and carotenoids were determined (Wintermans, De

Mots, 1965). The relative water content (RWC) was determined based on the method of Tambussi and colleagues (Tambussiet al., 2005). The determination of soluble sugars was carried out by the anthrone-sulfuric acid method (Azizov et al., 2019).

Data analysis and statistical analysis were conducted using Microsoft Excel. Statistical analysis was performed with the aid of the Statgraphics Plus 5.1 statistical package. The means of values were compared by Duncan's multiple range test ($p=0.05$).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To develop new, pure lines, salt tolerance of hybrids and parental forms was assessed based on physiological indices in the grain-filling stage of the vegetation. When studying salt-tolerance of hybrids and parental forms, differences were detected in the relative amounts of chlorophyll (a+b), carotenoids, RWC, as well as the photochemical activity of chloroplasts. The effect of salt on the amount of chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b, and carotenoids, which are the main physiological indicators, is manifested in different ways in both hybrids and parental forms. Based on the changes in the amount of pigments under salinity, the parental forms Garabagh, Gobustan, and Sharg were more tolerant. Thus, at least a 10 %-decrease in the amount of chlorophyll (a+b) pigments due to the effect of salt was observed in these parental genotypes. Whereas, the most growth in carotenoids amounted to 4–7 % in these varieties. This process can be attributed to the increase in the protective function of carotenoids under salt stress.

Table 1. Physiological indices (photosynthetic pigments, RWC) of the parental and hybrid forms of wheat under 1 % NaCl* (mg/g fresh weight)

Wheat varieties	Chl(a+b)		Carotenoids		RWC	
	Control	NaCl	Control	NaCl	Control	NaCl
Gobustan	3.47	2.42	1.04	0.54	70.9	73.1
Mirbashir-128	2.95	2.03	1.03	0.95	75.5	74.9
Barakatli-95	3.29	1.61	1.08	0.97	71.9	74.2
Garabagh	2.55	2.71	1.05	0.69	89.5	83.6
Gyrmyzygul	3.57	1.56	0.87	0.74	88.9	80.8
Sharg	3.38	1.50	1.17	0.38	70.5	76.9
Garabagh×Gobustan	2.98	1.50	1.17	0.51	67.9	84.1
Gobustan×Barakatli-95	2.93	2.49	1.04	0.90	98.6	72.8
Gobustan×Gyrmyzygul	2.54	2.24	0.86	1.06	75.5	79.6
Barakatli-95×Gobustan	3.33	1.51	1.35	0.62	67.4	81.8
Gobustan×Garabagh	2.09	1.63	0.60	0.63	92.3	75.6
Garabagh×Mirbashir-128	2.26	1.75	0.57	0.29	94.8	79.5
Garabagh×Sharg	3.55	1.42	1.72	0.33	74.4	83.5

Note: * Each value represents the mean ±SD (standard deviation) for the mean n=3 independent experiments $p=0.05$

Table 2. Effect of NaCl on elements of the yield structure of durum and bread winter wheat varieties under the conditions of a growing experiment

Wheat varieties	Plant height, sm		number of grains per ear		grain weight, g		crop losses, %
	control	NaCl	control	NaCl	control	NaCl	
Gobustan	90±2	68±1	62±3	45±4	3.6	1.4	62
Mirbashir-128	105±4	73±1	42±2	18±1	4.6	1.2	74
Barakatli-95	85±2	75±2	68±3	29±2	3.5	1.7	52
Garabagh	80±2	62±1	41±1	32±2	2.2	1.5	32
Gyrmyzygul	72±1	57±2	46±2	22±1	3.1	2.4	23
Sharg	110±4	70±3	32±2	19±1	4.2	1.4	67
Garabagh×Gobustan	120±3	65±2	52±3	36±2	1.4	1.1	22
Gobustan×Barakatli-95	76±2	100±4	32±2	20±1	2.8	2.2	22
Gobustan×Gyrmyzygul	118±4	70±2	34±1	27±2	2.9	2.3	21
Barakatli-95×Gobustan	78±1	63±1	40±2	21±1	1.9	1.6	10
Gobustan×Garabagh	80±1	60±2	38±1	34±2	4.2	2.8	34
Garabagh×Mirbashir-128	90±2	60±1	54±3	33±3	1.9	1.7	11
Garabagh×Sharg	90±2	70±2	60±2	22±2	3.2	1.3	60

Note: * Each value represents the mean ±SD (standard deviation) for the mean n=3 independent experiments p=0.05.

Fig. Influence of sodium chloride on sugar content in seedlings of maize varieties

Based on RWC values, Garabagh and Gobustan varieties had the highest water content. Water loss in these varieties did not decrease but increased by 3 %. The results obtained are presented in Table 1. Based on the amounts of chlorophyll (a+b), the hybrids, ♀Garabagh×♂Gobustan, ♀Garabagh×♂Mirbashir, ♀Garabagh×♂Sharg are more tolerant to salinity. An increase in the amount of carotenoids was also observed in these hybrids. The highest values for RWC were found in the hybrid forms, ♀Garabagh×♂Gobustan, ♀Barakatli-95×♂Gobustan, ♀Garabagh×♂Sharg. RWC was 10 % higher in these hybrids compared to others under stress. A 20 %-decrease in RWC was observed in the hybrid form, ♀Gobustan×♂Gyrmyzygul.

The first indicator of fluorescence in varieties grown in a saline environment is light energy. Energy loss occurs under salinity. In this case, the activity of the photosystem is reduced, which leads to the weakening development of the plant.

Based on the PS II activity, the parental forms,

Garabagh, Gobustan, and the hybrids, ♀Gobustan×Barakatli-95, ♀Gobustan×♂Garabagh, and ♀Gobustan×♂Sharg are more salt-tolerant.

One of the most useful indicators of wheat is grain yield. High salt concentrations contributed to a decrease in grain yield. Among the genotypes, according to this indicator, the most salt tolerant were the hybrids Barakatli-95×Gobustan and Garabagh×Mirbashir-128 (Table 2).

It revealed that under the influence of salt, germination and germination energy of maize seeds reduced. With the increase of sodium chloride concentration decreased the photochemical activity of chloroplasts and the content of photosynthetic pigments in seedlings.

Salinity could affect the chlorophyll concentration of leaves through inhibition of the synthesis of chlorophyll or acceleration of its degradation. Impairment of the carboxylation capacity, which in turn inhibits electron transport, is indicated by the measurements of chlorophyll fluorescence. A reduced quantum yield may result from a structural impact on PS II although some

authors (Lu, et al., 2002) found PS II to be highly tolerant to salinity stress. Salinity has been concluded to affect reaction centers of PS II either directly or via accelerated senescence. High external salt concentrations could affect thylakoid membranes by disrupting lipid bilayer or lipid-protein associations and thus, impair electron transport activity. The efficiency of the photochemical conversion of the PS II energy decreased with increasing salt concentrations. Some authors indicate a decrease in the root system function in plants exposed to salt stress. They assumed a more important role in the toxic effects of ions (Wang et al., 2012).

Under the conditions of salt stress, a slight increase in the content of soluble sugars was found in all genotypes of maize (Fig.).

In general, the growth and development of plants depend on the process of photosynthesis in their green organs. Therefore, environmental stressors affecting photosynthesis also affect growth and development (Villora et al., 1997). A positive correlation between the rate of photosynthesis and productivity has been found in various plants under salinity (Perez, et al., 1996).

The decrease in RWC due to stress indicates that the cell does not have the turgor necessary for the tension process to take place (Katterji et al., 1997). The response of plants to stressors is different, depending on the genetic material. Thus, the genetic material regulates the speed and consistency of protein synthesis required under stress. Some difficulties in the cultivation of salt-tolerant forms are attributed to the complexity and polygenic nature of genes. It is known that under salt stress, the external water potential decreases, the absorption of biogenic metal ions by the roots becomes difficult, and the chlorine and sodium ions have a toxic effect on plant metabolism. These three possible effects of salt stress have a detrimental effect on plant growth, development and yield. (Muhammad et al., 2015; Munns, et al., 2006). Osmotic stress is associated with the accumulation of ions in the soil solution, while malnutrition and the specific effects of ions are associated with the accumulation of ions, mainly sodium and chloride, to toxic levels which inhibits the availability of other important elements such as calcium and potassium. Toxic levels of sodium in plant organs damage biological membranes and subcellular organelles, reducing growth and causing abnormal development before plant death. Several physiological processes, such as photosynthesis, respiration, starch metabolism and fixation of nitrogen also disrupted in salt conditions, which leads to a decrease in crop productivity. In response to this, the plant synthesizes low molecular weight

solutes, including soluble carbohydrates for better absorption of water during salinity. Genotypes with a powerful genetic apparatus cope with this task and grow well in salt conditions. In the process of evolution, protective mechanisms against environmental stressors are formed in all organisms, including plants. Therefore, when assessing tolerance to stress factors, it is necessary to consider the individual characteristics of each plant genotype (9). NaCl (0.98 %) in the soil has been found to affect the physiological parameters of parental and hybrid forms differently.

CONCLUSION

Negative effects of salt stress were observed in the content of photosynthetic pigments, photochemical activity of PS II and RWC in parental and hybrid forms. The content of chl a, chl b, the activity of PSII, RWC and grain yield were higher in the parental forms, Garabagh, Gobustan, Barakatli-95, and in the hybrids, ♀Garabagh×♂Gobustan, ♀Barakatli-5×♂Gobustan, ♀Gobustan×♂Gyrmyzygul-and Garabagh×♂Mirbashir-128. Due to these advantages, using these varieties for future research on the development of salt-tolerant forms can be considered expedient.

Under conditions of salt stress, a slight increase in the content of soluble sugars was found in all genotypes of maize. The highest sugar content was observed in the hybrid Zagatala 68 x Gurur.

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Natrium xloridin buğda və qarğıdalı genotiplərinin morfofizioloji göstəricilərinə təsiri

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Azərbaycan Respublikası Elm və Təhsil Nazirliyi Molekulyar Biologiya və Biotexnologiyalar İnstitutunun Xloroplastların fotokimyəsi laboratoriyası, Bakı, Azərbaycan

İşin məqsədi buğda və qarğıdalı genotiplərinin fizioloji və biokimyəvi xüsusiyyətlərinə natrium xloridin təsirini öyrənmək, şoranlığa davamlı sortları müəyyən etmək olmuşdur. Buğda və qarğıdalının duza davamlı yeni sortlarının yaradılması üçün valideyn və hibrid bitkilərin fizioloji və biokimyəvi göstəricilərinin müqayisəli təhlili aparılmışdır. Valideyn formalarda və hibridlərdə xlorofilin və nisbi suyun miqdarı kimi fizioloji parametrlər tədqiq edilmişdir. Hibridlərin və valideyn formaların duza davamlılığını öyrənərkən, xlorofilin (a + b), karotinoidlərin və nisbi suyun miqdarında fərqlər aşkar edilmişdir. Əsas fizioloji göstəricilər olan xlorofil a, xlorofil b və karotinoidlərin miqdarına duzun təsiri həm hibridlərdə, həm də valideyn formalarında fərqli şəkildə özünü göstərmişdir. Dən dolma fazasında müəyyən edilən fizioloji göstəricilərə görə ən böyük tolerantlıq valideyn formalardan Qarabağ və Qobustanda və hibridlərdən ♀Qarabağ × ♂ Qobustan, ♀ Qarabağ × ♂ Mirbəşir, ♀ Qarabağ × ♂ Şərqdə müəyyən edilmişdir. Duzun təsirindən bütün qarğıdalı genotiplərində həll olunan şəkərlərin miqdarında bir qədər artım müşahidə edilmişdir. Şəkərin ən yüksək miqdarı Zaqatala 68 x Gürur hibridində qeydə alınmışdır.

Açar sözlər: Buğda, qarğıdalı, duzluluq, hibrid, genotip, xlorofil, karotinoid, tolerantlıq